

Power-Aware High-Capacity Elastic Optical Networks [Invited]

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The power consumption of telecommunication equipment has been identified as a relevant contributor to the global energy consumption. In fact, new-generation optical transponders employ power-intensive electronic application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) for digital signal processing (DSP). DSP design has traditionally prioritized meeting transmission requirements over power consumption optimization. In general, the evolutions of transmission techniques and network design have always been mainly driven by traffic increase; in this context, in order to operate network resources more efficiently, margin reduction has been investigated in the last years. Indeed, traditionally, high physical layer margins are used to ensure reliability over an extended period, resulting in overprovisioning the optical connections for both physical layer conditions and capacity. On the other hand, super-channels have emerged as a suitable solution for accommodating the continuous traffic growth. However, power consumption has not been deeply considered in the optimization of super-channel transmission. This paper first investigates power-efficiency of super-channels operated with designed and reduced margins. Low-margin operation is enabled by adapting sub-carrier spacing and filter bandwidth. Power-aware super-channel optimization is then experimentally demonstrated leveraging a 600 Gbit/s transponder in the SDN-controlled Elastic Optical Network (EON). The results have identified a trade-off between power consumption and spectrum-efficiency. Furthermore, the ongoing bandwidth demand has motivated the investigation of multi-band (MB) transmission for scaling the capacity of the existing infrastructures. However, novel networking devices (e.g., optical amplifiers operating beyond C and L bands) will affect the overall power consumption. In this context, experimental power analysis of Thulium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (TDFA) is performed based on the traffic load and corresponding configuration. The results show that TDFA power consumption varies with configuration and increases with output power.

1. INTRODUCTION

The predicted annual traffic growth of over 20% emphasizes the increasing impact of power consumption in telecommunication equipment on global energy usage. In fact, the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector constitutes 5-9% of global electricity usage [1] and is responsible for approximately 3% of worldwide CO₂ emissions [2], a level comparable to that of the global airline industry [3]. In the absence of proactive measures, the European Commission estimates that carbon footprint of the ICT sector could reach 14% of global greenhouse emissions by 2040 [1]. Moreover, the increasing expense of energy should serve as an incentive to investigate solutions that prioritize high energy efficiency and more effective utilization of available resources. Therefore, it is imperative to address energy savings while meeting the demands for high-speed traffic.

For given reasons, there is a rising interest in the research community in studying the power consumption of optical networks [4]. In general, the analysis of energy efficiency occurs at three levels: (1) component

level, accounting for power consumption of individual devices, such as transponders, optical amplifiers, etc.; (2) node level, influenced by various components and their functionalities within the network; and (3) network architecture level, considering the overall topology and involving efficient network planning, dynamic resource management, and control mechanisms that make the better use of networking equipment. Furthermore, power consumption reduction strategies could be classified into two main categories [4]: (1) energy-proportional strategies that involve dynamically scaling the power consumption of individual devices with the actual traffic load, and (2) sleep mode strategies that focus on transitioning the entire nodes or specific components into a low-power idle operation during periods of low traffic or inactivity. Hence, by analyzing the power consumption of the individual network devices and implementing these strategies, it is possible to optimize the network performance and realize substantial reductions in the overall power consumption.

Coherent technology has improved the utilization of the existing fiber infrastructures by offering flexibility in modulation format, bandwidth, bit rates, and channel spacing. This adaptability has enabled Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) to meet the varying traffic requirements (e.g., bandwidth) [5]. Current commercial transponders leverage coherent receivers and digital signal processing (DSP), performed by power-demanding and costly electronic application specific integrated circuits (ASICs), for modulation/demodulation and for mitigating several physical-layer impairments. Indeed, the DSP algorithms of such transponders are mainly operated to fulfill transmission requirements, with limited attention to the power consumption. In addition, the power consumption of these devices increases with the traffic load. On the other hand, high physical layer margins are traditionally used to account for modeling uncertainties and change in physical layer, thus to ensure reliability over long periods of time [6]–[9]. In fact, optical connections are overprovisioned for capacity and conditions in the physical layer, and remain unchanged over an extended period. Therefore, operating the optical networks with reduced margins significantly reduces the network costs, while increasing its spectral efficiency [7]–[15]. Moreover, the optimization of spectrum resources and capacity adaptation to actual traffic enables the implementation of energy-proportional strategies [15].

Super-channel transmission is a suitable method to efficiently address the increasing demand for higher data rates and enhanced network capacity [16]–[22]. However, optimizing super-channels presents significant challenges, particularly due to reduced spacing among sub-carrier central frequencies, leading to linear cross-talk, and narrow optical filtering [23], [24]. As a result, the overall quality of transmission (QoT) might be degraded. In the context of operating super-channels with reduced margins, appropriate operational modes (e.g., modulation formats) and transmission conditions (e.g., narrow filtering) have enabled significant saving of spectrum resources while increasing efficiency as reported in [15]. However, the energy efficiency of super-channels optimized for spectrum saving is yet to be thoroughly investigated. Moreover, trading-off between power consumption and spectral efficiency in the super-channel optimization has not been deeply considered.

In this work, which is an extended version of [25], we aim at investigating energy consumption of high-capacity optical networks, including multi-band (MB) transmission, and increasing their energy efficiency. We first analyze the impact of utilizing super-channels composed of different modulation formats and bit rates on power consumption. Then, the trade-off between power consumption of super-channels operating with design and reduced margins is investigated. The reduced margin operation (i.e., spectrum saving) is achieved by allowing the slight sub-carrier overlap and tight filtering as reported in [15]. Next, we propose and experimentally demonstrate an automatic procedure for power-aware super-channel optimization based on the bit rate requirements and the physical characteristics of a path (i.e., modulation format and its correlation to the optical reach). Experimental demonstration is conducted utilizing the 600 Gbit/s transponder in the EON testbed. Differently from [25], experiments are carried out considering super-channels from 600 Gbit/s to 1000 Gbit/s and the optical reach of 80 km, 160 km, 240 km and 320 km, respectively. Moreover, more details on the implemented control plane and agents, particularly on the spectrum saving procedure, is provided. In the context of MB transmission, the power analysis of Thulium Doped Fiber Amplifier (TDFA) is experimentally performed based on the traffic load and corresponding configuration.

2. FUTURE HIGH-CAPACITY OPTICAL NETWORKS

Despite the efforts to optimize the use of available spectrum resources (e.g., through reduced margin operation), the current optical

networks are approaching saturation due to the ongoing bandwidth demand [26]–[28]. Therefore, to scale the capacity of future optical networks, MB transmission and spatial-division multiplexing (SDM) represent two of the most promising solutions. However, exploiting the new wavelength bands, such as the S-band, provides the opportunity to make the best use of current single-mode fiber (SMF) infrastructures. This approach helps to postpone the installation of new fibers, required in the context of the SDM, while optimizing the efficiency of the existing networks. However, a substantial upgrade of current networks with the novel components operating beyond C and L bands is one of the many factors to be considered in the MB scenario. From the energy efficiency perspective, the introduction of the new network devices involved in the MB transmission (e.g., optical amplifiers for each band) will have implications on the overall power consumption.

Indeed, to understand the power consumption of future optical networks, it is first necessary to understand the constituent equipment shaping the network and analyze how their power consumption evolves over time. Optical amplifiers are essential components in optical networks, playing a critical role in extending the reach and improving the quality of transmitted signals. However, one of the key issues in MB networks is the lack of a single Rare-Erath Doped Fiber providing the amplification over multiple bands. For example, Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers (EDFAs) are responsible for amplifying the signals in C and L bands. The power consumption of EDFAs is a significant consideration in the design and operation of current optical networks, given that they constitute a relevant part of the power consumption of an optical link [29]. Moreover, EDFAs require pump lasers to provide the energy needed to amplify signals and their energy efficiency is influenced by the pump power level. Higher pump power generally leads to the higher power consumption [29]. On the other hand, Thulium Doped Fiber

```

module: openconfig-terminal-device
  +-rw terminal-device
  +-rw config
  +-ro state
  +-rw logical-channels
  | +-rw channel* [index]
  | | +-rw index                -> ../config/index
  | | +-rw config
  | | | +-rw index?             uint32
  | | | +-rw description?      string
  | | | +-rw admin-state?      oc-opt-types:admin-state-type
  | | | +-rw rate-class?       identityref
  | | | +-rw trib-protocol?     identityref
  | | | +-rw logical-channel-type? identityref
  | | +-ro state
  | | | +-ro index?            uint32
  | | | +-ro description?     string
  | | | +-ro admin-state?     oc-opt-types:admin-state-type
  | | | +-ro rate-class?      identityref
  | | | +-ro trib-protocol?    identityref
  | | | +-ro logical-channel-type? identityref
  | | | +-ro link-state?      enumeration
  | +-rw otn
  | | +-rw config
  | | +-ro state
  | | | +-ro pre-fec-ber
  | | | +-ro post-fec-ber
  | | | +-ro q-value
  | | | +-ro esnr
  | +-rw logical-channel-assignments
  | +-rw assignment* [index]
  | | +-rw index                -> ../config/index
  | | +-rw config
  | | +-ro state
  |
  augment /oc-platform:components/oc-platform:component:
    +-rw optical-channel
    +-rw config
    | +-rw frequency?           oc-opt-types:frequency-type
    | +-rw target-output-power? decimal64
    | +-rw operational-mode?    uint16
    | +-rw line-port?           -> /oc-platform:components/component/name
    +-ro state
    +-ro frequency?            oc-opt-types:frequency-type
    +-ro target-output-power?  decimal64
    +-ro operational-mode?     uint16
    +-ro line-port?            -> /oc-platform:components/component/name
    +-ro group-id?             uint32
    +-ro output-power
    +-ro input-power
    +-ro laser-bias-current
    +-ro chromatic-dispersion
    +-ro polarization-mode-dispersion
    +-ro second-order-polarization-mode-dispersion
    +-ro polarization-dependent-loss
  
```

Fig. 1. The tree view of OpenConfig YANG model for transponders

Amplifiers (TDFAs) are identified to be suitable for the S-band amplification [30], [31] and are commercially available [32]. TDFAs are generally equipped with multiple pump lasers, thus introducing additional complexities in their configuration and operation. Furthermore, their power consumption has not been yet investigated in the literature. Therefore, another contribution of this paper is the preliminary experimental power analysis of TDFA based on the traffic load. This investigation can potentially motivate dynamic power adjustment mechanisms to optimize the power consumption of TDFAs based on real-time traffic conditions across all active bands.

3. SDN CONTROL AND DATA PLANE MODELING

The adoption of Software Defined Networking (SDN) in optical networks control has been driven by the need for flexibility and automation. SDN enables the description, abstraction, configuration, and monitoring of optical network devices solely through software [33]. Traditionally, the network devices have been controlled and managed by proprietary software and hardware solutions. However, in the context of the SDN networking, the devices are disaggregated into two logical sections: the data plane representing the physical infrastructure, and the control plane, responsible for configuration and monitoring. Devices are typically connected to an SDN controller through an agent, acting as a local controller. Then, the SDN controller leverages dedicated protocols and agents to make optimized decisions based on the complete state of the network. NETCONF [34] is a model-based protocol for implementing the control of optical devices. YANG (Yet Another Next Generation) [35], developed in the context of NETCONF, plays a crucial role in describing the data plane. The YANG data models employed in this work encompass optical transponders, power consumption information, and MB optical amplifiers. Description for each is provided below. Then, the SDN control for configuration and monitoring is enabled through `<edit-config>` and `<get>` NETCONF messages, respectively.

The OpenConfig YANG model for optical transponders in Fig. 1 – here assumed as a reference model – facilitates the configuration and monitoring of main transponder parameters in a vendor-agnostic manner through the use of the NETCONF protocol [36]. It consists of two main sections: `<terminal-device>` and `<components>`. The former comprises four primary blocks: (1) the `<config>` block, which encapsulates configurable hardware parameters; (2) the `<state>` block, responsible for storing state information related to the `<config>` parameters; (3) the `<otn>` block, tasked with monitoring key state parameters of optical signal quality (e.g., pre-FEC-BER); and (4) the `<logical-channel-assignment>` block, designed for mapping physical ports elements to the logical channels. The latter defines: (1) the `<config>` block responsible for configuration of optical channels (e.g., frequency, target output power, operational mode); and (2) the `<state>` for monitoring of the optical channel parameters. To maintain stability and optimize performance, proprietary transmission parameters such as bit rates, modulation formats and Forward Error Correction (FEC) techniques are mapped to operational (OP) modes, rather than being defined within the model itself [15], [37]–[39]. This study employs the traditional OpenConfig

```

module: openconfig-platform
  +--rw components
    +--rw component* [name]
      +--rw name                -> ../config/name
      +--rw config
        | +--rw name?          string
      +--ro state
        | +--ro name?          string
        | +--ro type?          union
        | +--ro used-power?    uint32

```

Fig. 2. The tree view of OpenConfig `<platform>` data model

```

module: openconfig-multiband-optical-amplifiers
  +--rw multiband-optical-amplifiers
    +--rw optical-amplifier
      +--rw amplifier* [id]
        +--rw id                -> ../config/id
        +--rw config
          | +--rw id?           uint32
          | +--rw name?        string
          | +--rw amp-mode?    identityref
          | +--rw target-output-power? decimal64
          | +--rw max-output-power? decimal64
          | +--rw target-gain? decimal64
          | +--rw active?      boolean
          | +--rw laser-diode-pumps
          |   +--rw pump-LD* [pump-id]
          |     +--rw pump-id          uint32
          |     +--rw pump-bias-current? decimal64
          |     +--rw pump-mode?      identityref
          |     +--rw pump-temperature? decimal64
          |     +--rw pump-TEC-current? decimal64
          | +--ro input-power-total? decimal64
          | +--ro output-power-total? decimal64
          | +--ro noise-figure?      decimal64
          | +--ro optical-return-loss? decimal64
          | +--ro fiber-type-profile? identityref
          | +--ro component?         leafref
          | +--ro ingress-port?     leafref
          | +--ro egress-port?      leafref
        +--ro state
          +--ro id?                 uint32
          +--ro name?              string
          +--ro operating-band
            | +--ro amplifier-band? identityref
            | +--ro lower-frequency? oc-opt-types:frequency-type
            | +--ro upper-frequency? oc-opt-types:frequency-type
          +--ro type?              identityref
          +--ro amp-mode?          identityref
          +--ro target-output-power? decimal64
          +--ro max-output-power? decimal64
          +--ro target-gain?      decimal64
          +--ro active?            boolean
          +--ro laser-diode-pumps
            | +--ro pump-LD* [pump-id]
            |   +--ro pump-id          uint32
            |   +--ro pump-bias-current? decimal64
            |   +--ro pump-mode?      identityref
            |   +--ro pump-temperature? decimal64
            |   +--ro pump-TEC-current? decimal64
            +--ro input-power-total? decimal64
            +--ro output-power-total? decimal64
            +--ro noise-figure?      decimal64
            +--ro optical-return-loss? decimal64
            +--ro fiber-type-profile? identityref
            +--ro component?         leafref
            +--ro ingress-port?     leafref
            +--ro egress-port?      leafref

```

Fig. 3. The tree view of data model for MB optical amplifiers

data model for transponders, treating each sub-carrier of the super-channel independently for configuration enforcement, thus allowing the validation of the optimization procedures using commercial transponders. Future research will investigate the comprehensive management of super-channels using evolved data models.

Incorporating power consumption awareness into optical network control contributes to the overall energy efficiency. It enables adaptive and dynamic resource management, aligning network operation with the current power requirements and traffic conditions. The OpenConfig `<platform>` YANG model includes information on power consumption and it is described in the Fig. 2 [36].

Finally, in the context of MB transmission, standard OpenConfig YANG model for optical amplifiers is enhanced in [40], enabling configuration of the key operational parameters (e.g., selection of pumping currents to achieve target output power) as indicated in Fig. 3. The data model presents a list of optical amplifiers (e.g., one per band), including their type (e.g., TDFA), operational mode (e.g., DYNAMIC_GAIN), target output power and target gain. It incorporates a list of pump lasers and their corresponding bias currents, enabling proper configuration of optical amplifiers employing multiple pumps. Moreover, the `<state>` data provides the information on the operating band (e.g., the S-band).

4. POWER CONSUMPTION ANALYSIS AND POWER EFFICIENCY

This section provides insight into power analysis in the context of: (1) the proposed procedure designed for the power-aware super-channels, accounting for the designed and reduced margin operation aligned with the selected OP modes and optical reach; and (2) the experimental TDFA power consumption based on the TDFA output power and corresponding configuration.

demonstrated in Fig. 4 step 1. Regardless of the super-channel type, the spectrum saving procedure starts by optimizing a single sub-carrier at the time (e.g., left-hand sub-carrier) as shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b) step 2. Therefore, the bandwidth saving per sub-carrier is defined as a sum of (x, y) values. Value x indicates the number of 6.25 GHz slots saved from filter border, while y represents savings on the adjacent sub-carrier side. For two alike sub-carriers (i.e., homogeneous super-channels), total bandwidth saving is a sum of (x, y, x) values representing the multiple of 6.25 GHz each, as shown in Fig. 4 (a) step 3. On the other hand, while the sub-carrier overlap must be symmetrical, the savings on the filter side may not be – in the context of hybrid super-channels. Therefore, after optimizing the left-hand sub-carrier for spectrum saving (i.e., determining x and y values), both sub-carriers are shifted towards the opposite filter border (i.e., right) to assess the spectrum saved on that side (i.e., w value), as depicted in Fig. 4 (b) step 3. Then, their spectrum

Fig. 5. Data and control plane reference scenario

Fig. 4. Spectrum saving optimization procedure of (a) homogeneous and (b) hybrid super-channels

A. Power-aware super-channel optimization procedure

First, the spectrum saving optimization procedure for low-margin super-channel operation is outlined. Two types of super-channels are defined: (1) homogeneous super-channels, characterized by identical sub-carriers in terms of the OP mode (i.e., bit rate, modulation format and slot width); and (2) hybrid super-channels that consist of sub-carriers with different OP modes. A 700 Gbit/s connection is an example of a hybrid super-channel, achieved by employing two sub-carriers operating at 400 Gbit/s and 300 Gbit/s, respectively. Then, reduced margin operation is enabled by allowing the tight filtering and the slight sub-carrier overlap. This is achieved by moving the Tx/Rx sub-carriers towards either left or right filter border in steps of 6.25 GHz. The pre-forward error correction – FEC – bit error rate – BER degradation resulting from linear cross-talk and filtering effects is then continuously monitored to ensure acceptable QoT.

The SDN controller initiates the configuration of either homogeneous ($OP_x OP_x$) or hybrid ($OP_x OP_y$) super-channels by ensuring sufficient spectrum resources are reserved along the optical path, such that the sub-carriers do not experience any degradation of the signal, as

occupation is reduced by a sum of (x, y, y, w) values upon optimization (Fig. 4 (b) step 4). For example, the saving configuration $(2, 1, 1, 0)$ indicates that 18.75 GHz is reduced by optimizing the left-hand sub-carrier [i.e., $(2 + 1) \times 6.25$ GHz steps], while 6.25 GHz is saved from the right-hand one, resulting in total saving of 25 GHz. This asymmetry results from using different OP modes and the considerably different impact filtering effects and cross-talk have on these sub-carriers.

The spectrum saving procedure attempts to optimize the super-channels for the maximum acceptable saving, identified to be 37.5 GHz. Configurations corresponding to such saving are $(3, 0, 0, 3)$, $(2, 1, 1, 2)$, $(1, 2, 2, 1)$ and $(0, 3, 3, 0)$. Therefore, super-channels are (re-)configured according to the appropriate saving combination, and corresponding pre-FEC-BER values are collected. The configuration with the lowest pre-FEC-BER is selected to ensure the best QoT and is considered acceptable if it falls below the predefined threshold (TH) for error-free operation. In cases where this criterion is not met (i.e., pre-FEC-BER > TH), lower spectrum-saving configurations, such as those corresponding to 25 GHz saving, are explored. Therefore, the spectrum saving optimization procedure is employed within the context of power-aware super-channel optimization to enable low-margin operation.

The procedure proposed to identify the most power-efficient super-channel configuration during provisioning or inventory validation relies on the NETCONF protocol and the data models outlined in the previous section for sub-carrier (re-)configuration and monitoring of their corresponding power consumption and pre-FEC-BER values. Initially, the SDN controller accounts for the super-channel bit rate and optical reach, reflecting the traffic requirements and availability of modulation formats due to the physical characteristics of the path. For example, high-order modulation formats become unavailable as the optical reach is extended. Furthermore, nominal spectrum resources are reserved along the selected path (e.g., 150 GHz for two 75 GHz wide sub-carriers) as described in Fig. 4 step 1. Therefore, the suitable homogeneous and/or hybrid super-channels are computed.

Typically, the SDN controller configures the optical channel parameters, including OP modes, Tx/Rx central frequencies, and filter parameters, such as switched bandwidth, for each connection. However, in the network scenario where multiple combinations of the OP modes satisfy the bit-rate and modulation format requirements, it may be necessary for the SDN controller to perform multiple configurations to reach the optimal solution (e.g., in terms of the power-efficiency), introducing the additional complexities and potentially causing scalability issues. This is further accentuated in the context of low-margin operation, where optimal sub-carrier spacing and filter parameters need to be determined to maximize the saved spectrum. To address this, super-channel configuration is enforced directly by the transceivers' local agent, utilizing `<edit-config>` NETCONF message and `<components>` YANG model, effectively reducing the SDN controller involvement. Control plane reference scenario is shown in Fig. 5. Super-channels are first considered operating with the designed margins, followed then by the low-margin operation as described above. Power consumption and pre-FEC-BER monitoring information are obtained after each super-channel (re)-configuration regardless of the spectrum-efficiency, relying on the `<platform>` and `<terminal-device>` YANG models, respectively. Finally, the procedure yields two optimal super-channel configurations - one optimizing power saving, and the other prioritizing spectrum occupancy. The SDN controller then selects the appropriate configuration based on network requirements or operational policy.

Finally, the overall power consumption of the transmission system is defined as a sum of power consumptions attributed to the optical transponder, optical amplifiers, and WSSs. This aggregate value is influenced by super-channel configuration, and the number of optical amplifiers (N) and WSSs (M) employed in the system: $P_{total} = P_{transponder} + N \times P_{amplifier} + M \times P_{WSS}$. Considering that optical amplifiers consume around 15 W (e.g., WDM LIGHT EDFA), and WSSs (e.g., Lumentum) consume around 12 W, and that an optical line system hosts tens of channels, the main contribution to the power consumption is given by the optical transponders. Thus, the experimental analysis in the considered testbed will focus on their power-efficiency.

B. TDFA power consumption characterization

The adopted TDFA is equipped with three pump lasers: a main pump laser, pumping in the backward direction, and two sub-pump lasers, responsible for forward pumping. The device offers two driving modes: (1) Automatic Current Control (ACC) enabling pumping currents to remain constant despite the input power fluctuations; and (2) Automatic Light Control (ALC) allowing the control of the TDFA by configuring constant target output power. The main pump laser could be configured to both ACC and ALC modes, while the remaining two operate in ACC mode by design. Furthermore, the main pump and the first sub-pump operate within a range of 0 mA to 560 mA, whereas the remaining sub-pump functions in a range from 0 mA to 190 mA. The

Fig. 6. The experimental setup for power consumption characterization of the TDFA

mode, target output power and pumping configuration relies on NETCONF protocol and YANG model for MB optical amplifiers described in the previous section.

The experimental setup for power consumption characterization based on the total input power, wavelength, pumping configuration, and total output power is described in Fig. 6. The tunable S-band source, operating in a spectral region from 1490 nm to 1520 nm, is attenuated

using the Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) to obtain an input power range from -35 dBm to -5 dBm, with a 5 dBm step. The main pump is set to operate in a constant output power mode (ALC), and the configuration of the other two pumps is fine-tuned to bring the output power to a desired level. Pump two is adjusted in steps of 70 mA, reaching up to 560 mA, while pump three values are varied in increments of 10 mA, ranging up to 190 mA, to allow for a finely tuned granularity in output power. Furthermore, an electrical power analyzer for power consumption monitoring is employed. Then, for all combinations of wavelength, total input power, and pumping currents, the target output power and corresponding power consumption values are collected. Finally, results are analyzed in the context of TDFA output power and pumping configuration in the following section.

5. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND RESULTS

A. Results on power-aware super-channels

The experimental super-channels optimization has been conducted in the context of the optical data plane reported in the bottom of Fig. 5 to determine the power characteristics based on their operation and varying the optical reach. Two optical channels are aggregated at the Tx side of a Fujitsu 1Finity T600 transponder to build a homogenous or a hybrid super-channel of desired capacity, ranging from 600 Gbit/s to 1000 Gbit/s. The super-channel then traverses the first Wavelength Selective Switch (WSS) filter and is sent to a first amplifier to ensure both optical channels are entering optical fiber spans with the power of 0 dBm each. Next, several optical fiber spans of 80 km ($N = 1$), 160 km ($N = 2$), 240 km ($N = 3$) and 320 km ($N = 4$) are traversed to achieve a target optical reach. Finally, the super-channel enters the second WSS,

```

<components xmlns="http://openconfig.net/yang/platform">
  <component>
    <name>shelf-1</name>
    <config>
      <name>shelf-1</name>
    </config>
    <state>
      <name>shelf-1</name>
      <type xmlns:opt="http://openconfig.net/yang/platform-types">opt:CHASSIS</type>
      <used-power>260</used-power>
    </state>
  </component>
</components>
  
```

Fig. 7. `<get>` NETCONF message reporting the total `<used-power>` for OP2 optical channel

followed by an amplifier, before reaching Rx, where coherent detection is performed. Moreover, the testbed employs an electrical power analyzer for power consumption monitoring.

Total power consumption of a transponder consists of a fixed component, representing the idle state when transponder is not operating, and the transmission power, a dynamic component that varies according to the utilized OP mode (i.e., modulation format).

Table 1. OP modes and corresponding transmission power consumption for the optical reach of 80 km

OP Mode	Bit Rate [Gbit/s]	Modulation Format	Slot [GHz]	Power [W]	Efficiency [W/Gbit/s]
2	500	DP-32QAM	75	104	0.21
3	400	DP-16QAM	75	92	0.23
5	300	8PSK-2	75	82	0.27
6	200	8PSK	75	80	0.4
7	200	DP-16QAM	50	72	0.36

Table 2. Evolution of the pre-FEC-BER values and transmission power consumption obtained according to the optical reach, selected OP modes and the super-channel operation (designed and reduced margin)

		80 km		160 km		240 km		320 km	
1000 Gbit/s	OP2	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	137.5 GHz	150 GHz	> TH
	OP2	6.5E-3 7.9E-3	2.1E-2 2.3E-2	9.0E-3 1.1E-2	2.3E-2 2.5E-2	1.4E-2 1.5E-2	1.8E-2 1.4E-2	2.3E-2 2.3E-2	
900 Gbit/s	OP2	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	131.25 GHz	150 GHz	137.5 GHz
	OP3	6.9E-3 5.8E-4	2.3E-2 2.9E-3	9.3E-3 9.0E-4	2.4E-2 3.8E-3	1.3E-2 1.3E-3	2.1E-2 6.6E-3	2.3E-2 4.6E-3	2.3E-2 1.9E-2
800 Gbit/s	OP2	150 GHz	118.75 GHz	150 GHz	118.75 GHz	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	131.25 GHz
	OP5	6.4E-3 2.7E-5	2.1E-2 5.7E-4	8.9E-3 6.6E-5	2.2E-2 1.7E-4	1.4E-2 1.3E-4	1.9E-2 1.6E-4	2.3E-2 6.5E-4	2.3E-2 8.0E-3
	OP3	150 GHz	125 GHz						
	OP3	4.3E-4 5.9E-4	7.2E-3 1.0E-2	6.7E-4 1.2E-3	2.3E-3 2.4E-2	1.3E-3 1.7E-3	1.7E-2 1.3E-2	3.3E-3 4.6E-3	2.3E-2 2.2E-2
700 Gbit/s	OP2	150 GHz	118.75 GHz	150 GHz	118.75 GHz	150 GHz	125 GHz	150 GHz	131.25 GHz
	OP6	6.3E-3 9.3E-8	2.1E-2 3.9E-6	9.0E-3 2.9E-7	2.3E-2 2.3E-6	1.3E-2 1.8E-6	1.9E-2 6.0E-6	2.3E-2 3.9E-5	2.3E-2 1.4E-3
	OP2	125 GHz	100 GHz	125 GHz	100 GHz	125 GHz	106.25 GHz	125 GHz	112.5 GHz
	OP7	6.6E-3 1.0E-5	2.3E-2 5.3E-3	9.3E-3 2.8E-5	2.2E-2 2.5E-4	1.4E-2 6.1E-5	1.2E-2 2.6E-3	2.3E-2 2.7E-4	2.3E-2 3.9E-3
	OP3	150 GHz	118.75 GHz						
	OP5	3.2E-4 2.3E-6	4.3E-3 2.0E-4	5.8E-4 6.4E-5	9.2E-3 7.5E-5	1.2E-3 1.4E-4	1.6E-2 2.8E-4	3.3E-3 6.3E-4	1.1E-2 2.3E-2
600 Gbit/s	OP3	150 GHz	118.75 GHz						
	OP6	3.2E-4 8.2E-8	3.2E-3 5.6E-7	5.9E-4 3.0E-7	9.3E-3 3.4E-6	1.1E-3 1.5E-6	1.6E-2 4.3E-6	3.3E-3 2.1E-5	1.6E-2 3.1E-3
	OP3	125 GHz	100 GHz						
	OP7	3.5E-4 9.4E-6	6.8E-3 1.1E-3	6.2E-4 2.0E-5	8.1E-3 5.2E-3	1.2E-3 5.4E-5	2.4E-2 5.2E-3	3.5E-3 2.6E-4	2.2E-2 8.2E-3
	OP5	150 GHz	112.5 GHz						
	OP5	2.2E-5 2.2E-5	1.1E-3 1.2E-3	4.0E-5 6.2E-5	4.6E-3 4.2E-3	9.5E-5 1.4E-4	2.4E-3 2.2E-3	4.9E-4 6.7E-4	3.9E-3 5.3E-3

Throughout the remainder of the paper, we refer to the power consumption as transmission power. Therefore, the total device power consumption is the sum of the fixed power (around 156 W), and the transmission power. The `<get>` NETCONF message reporting the total `<used-power>` for OP2 optical channel is shown in Fig. 7. Table 1 shows the information on the bit rate, modulation format, bandwidth occupation, and finally, the respective (transmission) power consumption and power-efficiency according to the selected OP mode for the optical reach of 80 km. Power-efficiency represents the amount of power consumed per unit of data (i.e., 1 Gbit/s) and it is calculated as a ratio of power consumption and bit rate. For example, OP3 utilizes DP-16QAM and 75 GHz of spectrum and consumes 92 W to transmit 400 Gbit/s, demonstrating the efficiency of 0.23 W/Gbit/s. While an OP mode may suggest better energy-efficiency, that solely is not an indicator of reduced power consumption (e.g., OP2 requires less power to transmit 1 Gbit/s, however, consumes more overall power compared to the other OP modes). Therefore, a fair assessment of energy-efficiency should consider OP modes with the same bit rate (i.e., OP6 and OP7). In such comparisons, the (super-)channels exhibiting greater power efficiency coincide with the ones consuming less power. The results from Table 1 show 30.77% variation in power consumption levels for two extreme configurations (i.e., OP2 and OP7 optical channels, consuming 104 W and 72 W, respectively). Therefore, the impact of utilizing super-channels composed of different modulation formats and bit rates on power consumption is investigated.

Super-channel power-efficiency depends on the combination of the selected OP modes for achieving the desired bit rate. For example, 1000 Gbit/s super-channel could be obtained by utilizing two OP2 sub-carriers, while 800 Gbit/s super-channel may result from a combination

of OP2 OP5 sub-carriers, or two OP3 sub-carriers. Table 2 provides pre-FEC-BER values for the selected OP modes and super-channel transmission power consumption according to the super-channel capacity (i.e., bit rate) and optical reach. Furthermore, within a column representing a specific optical reach (e.g., 80 km), the left column corresponds to the designed margin operation, while the right one shows the results of the low-margin operation, as indicated by the super-channel spectrum occupation. For instance, for a 900 Gbit/s super-channel and optical reach of 320 km, 150 GHz refers to the designed margins, whereas 137.5 GHz corresponds to the reduced margins scenario.

The study of super-channel power consumption introduces several implications on the control plane operation, according to the network requirements or operational policies. Power consumption optimization can be achieved by identifying the most power-efficient super-channel among the ones operating with designed margins, given that they satisfy the same bit rate requirements. Consider a 700 Gbit/s super-channel, whose capacity can be obtained in three different configurations involving two sub-carriers: (1) OP2 and OP6; (2) OP2 and OP7; and (3) OP3 and OP5. The OP2 OP7 super-channel demonstrates the highest power efficiency for all optical link lengths, except for 240 km, where the OP3 OP5 configuration proves to be the most power-efficient. Moreover, designed margin operation allows the energy optimization to be performed a priori depending on the exploited modulation format, by storing the power consumption information collected during the inventory validation in e.g., look-up tables. On the other hand, the most spectrum-efficient one is the OP2 OP7 super-channel.

Margin reduction enables significant spectrum savings; however, it also leads to higher power consumption for all considered super-

Table 3. TDFA power consumption based on the traffic load and required output power

# ch	input [dBm]	0 dBm/channel						8 dBm/channel							
		output [dBm]	p2 [mA]	p3 [mA]	power [W]	p2 [mA]	p3 [mA]	power [W]	output [dBm]	p2 [mA]	p3 [mA]	power [W]	p2 [mA]	p3 [mA]	power [W]
1	-20	0	70	50	11.97	140	40	12.27	8	140	120	12.79	490	70	15.14
2	-16.98	3	140	60	12.41	280	50	13.34	11.04	350	160	14.76	490	130	15.62
3	-15.22	4.77	210	50	12.82	350	40	13.81	12.77	350	170	14.85	420	150	15.23
4	-13.97	6	280	50	13.32	420	40	14.38	14.02	490	190	16.13	560	170	16.48

channels. Although we do not have access to how the transceiver is designed, this power consumption increase can find explanation in a higher workload of the FEC and also of some DSP functionalities such as carrier recovery when pre-FEC-BER increases. As the spectrum occupation decreases, the varying impacts on power consumption are observed. For example, regarding a 600 Gbit/s super-channel, composed of two OP5 sub-carriers, the power consumption increases from 2 W to 6 W according to the optical reach, which might be considered insignificant. Therefore, prioritizing spectrum efficiency becomes more beneficial. On the other hand, utilizing two OP3 sub-carriers for an 800 Gbit/s super-channel low-margin operation leads to 8.82%, 10.24%, 9.66% and 9.13% increase in power consumption as we increase the length of optical connections. Thus, the designed margin operation might be preferred. It is important to note that the main contribution to the more significant increase in the overall power consumption comes from sub-carriers operating closer to the pre-defined TH of 2.5E-2 (i.e., OP2 and OP3 optical channels). For example, 900 Gbit/s connection presents pre-FEC-BER values of 6.9E-3 for OP2 and 5.8E-4 for OP3 sub-carriers considering 80 km optical reach. Once the spectrum saving optimization is performed, these values increase to 2.3E-2 and 2.9E-3, respectively, resulting in 6.31% higher power consumption. However, in some super-channel configurations, such as OP2 OP6 and at optical reach of 240 km and 320 km, there is no variance in power consumption between designed and low-margin operations. This is because the power required to operate OP2 mode is already accounted for under the designed margins. Another similar example would be a 1000 Gbit/s super-channel. This observation is important as it implies that the power consumption might increase as the other OP modes start operating closer to the minimum performance beyond the maximum considered optical reach of 320 km.

Therefore, trading-off between power- and spectrum-efficiency could potentially enable energy savings. To navigate this trade-off, the introduction of a threshold describing power savings could be proposed. The network architecture and number of optical transponders used should be considered when determining the proper value. Therefore, when the power reduction falls below the determined threshold, the spectrum-saving approach takes priority. Otherwise, prioritizing power efficiency is preferable. This approach takes into consideration the capacity challenges in the current optical networks, providing a balanced strategy for optimizing both power consumption and spectrum utilization based on the specific network conditions.

Moreover, the proposed procedure drives the energy-proportional strategies that involve re-configuring super-channels to the actual traffic load and enabling power consumption optimization. It has been reported that traffic exhibits substantial fluctuations over a 24-hour period, decreasing by as much as 50-60% during nighttime [41]. Therefore, re-configuring the super-channel from e.g., 1000 Gbit/s to 600 Gbit/s could save 18.32% of power for 80 km connections. Furthermore, in scenarios where additional spectrum resources are made available through activation of other bands (e.g., the S-band), understanding the power efficiency of networking devices operating

within those bands is necessary. Therefore, the TDFA power consumption analysis is detailed in the following subsection.

B. TDFA power consumption based on traffic load

This section provides the insight into the power consumption of the adopted TDFA based on the traffic load and output power requirements. It has been observed that the power consumption is independent of wavelength, and fluctuates from around 12 W to 16 W based on the output power to be achieved, resulting in a 25% variation. It does not directly depend on total input power (i.e., the same power consumption variation could be observed for input power ranging from -35 dBm to -5 dBm, with a granularity of 5 dBm), however, the input power will drive the pumping configuration according to the output power requirements, which will affect the power consumption. The output signal power is proportional to the TDFA pumps, indicating that as the pumping currents increase, so does the output power. However, since the TDFA employs multiple pumps, their particular combination (e.g., increasing one pump, while decreasing the other) will determine the exact output power, and therefore the power consumption.

Table 3 presents the total input power according to the number of channels operating in the S-band, pumping configurations (i.e., pump two and pump three currents) necessary to obtain the requested output power, and the resulting power consumption. It is split into two parts, with the left column corresponding to obtaining 0dBm/channel, and the right one with appropriate configurations (i.e., total output power, pump two and pump three) to achieve 8 dBm/channel. In general, the TDFA power consumption increases with the increase in total output power, therefore with higher pump values. However, due to the intrinsic redundancy of the TDFA, multiple pumping configurations can result in the same output power. Therefore, two pumping configurations to obtain same total output power are identified, and their impact on the power consumption is analyzed. For example, to achieve an output power of 8 dBm for a single channel with an input

```
<multiband-optical-amplifiers xmlns="http://openconfig.net/yang/optical-amplifier">
  <optical-amplifier>
    <amplifier>
      <id>1</id>
      <config>
        <id>1</id>
        <name>TDFA</name>
        <amp-mode>CONSTANT_POWER</amp-mode>
        <target-output-power>8.0</target-output-power>
        <active>true</active>
        <laser-diode-pumps>
          <pump-LD>
            <pump-id>2</pump-id>
            <pump-bias-current>140.0</pump-bias-current>
          </pump-LD>
          <pump-LD>
            <pump-id>3</pump-id>
            <pump-bias-current>120.0</pump-bias-current>
          </pump-LD>
        </laser-diode-pumps>
      </config>
    </amplifier>
  </optical-amplifier>
</multiband-optical-amplifiers>
```

Fig. 8. `<edit-config>` NETCONF message for TDFA configuration

power of -20 dBm, two pumping configurations could be utilized: (1) 140 mA and 120 mA; and (2) 490 mA and 70 mA, for pump two and pump three, respectively. Fig. 8 represent the `<edit-config>` NETCONF message to enforce the former TDFA configuration. Comparison between the two shows 15.52% higher power consumption when the latter is utilized. Moreover, it has been observed that the increase in pump two values contributes to consuming more power compared to higher pump three values. For instance, to achieve 6 dBm of total output power (e.g., 0 dBm each for four operating signals), 280 mA and 50 mA pumping configuration could be utilized. In contrast, as an example, configuring the pumps to 140 mA and 120 mA allows for achieving a higher output power of 8 dBm for a single channel. However, the power consumption is lower when higher optical output power is required, since the pump two decreases from 280 mA to 140 mA, despite the increase in pump three values from 50 mA to 120 mA. Therefore, different pumping selection results in slightly different power consumption of the TDFA. The main pump laser works in constant output power mode, however, it can be operated in the constant current mode (i.e., as the remaining two pumps), potentially impacting the overall power-efficiency.

Finally, in the context of MB transmission, amplification stages need to be re-built to account for dedicated amplifiers per band (e.g., TDFA for S-band). Therefore, the number of optical amplifiers in the future optical networks will increase. Their power consumption is an important aspect when determining the total energy requirements of the network. This first analysis drives the potential for the dynamic SDN-controlled power adjustment mechanisms for optimization of the TDFA power consumption based on real-time traffic conditions (e.g., number of channels operating in the S-band). However, it is necessary to investigate the energy-efficiency of other MB networking devices. Moreover, power-efficiency could be further optimized when selecting the pumping configuration. However, the impact of different pump values on QoT parameters (e.g., OSNR) should be taken into consideration.

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, power consumption is first analyzed in the context of the super-channels operating with designed and reduced margins, respectively. Power-aware super-channel optimization procedure, proposed to identify the most power- and spectrum-efficient super-channel configurations, has been successfully demonstrated through experiments in the SDN-controlled EON testbed. Results show that spectrum-efficient super-channels lead to higher power consumption. Moreover, the trade-off between spectrum-efficiency and power consumption has been observed, potentially enabling optimization strategies tailored to the network requirements. Future work will include the theoretical analysis of the relationship between power consumption and spectrum optimization. Then, the experimental TDFA power consumption analysis is performed according to the traffic load and corresponding pumping configuration. Results identified that the TDFA power consumption increases with the output power, and depends on the selected pump values. Therefore, TDFA power consumption could be optimized by balancing the traffic load, and selecting more energy-efficient pumping configuration through the use of machine learning techniques.

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